

THE DETECTION AND DETERMINATION OF PYRIDINE BASES IN DENATURED SPIRIT.

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Three methods have been described for the detection and determination of pyridine bases in denatured spirit depending upon the use of 6% CdCl_2 solution, titration with H_2SO_4 with congo-red as an external indicator and colorimetric experiments with the use of cyanogen bromide-aniline reagent.

Spirit is ordinarily denatured in India by the addition of 0.5% light caoutchoucine and 0.5% pyridine bases of guaranteed mineral origin. The "pyridine bases" or commercial 90/160 pyridine is a tar product conforming to the Government of India specifications and consisting principally of pyridine, picolines, lutidines and collidines.

In the examination of denatured spirits, the amounts of light caoutchoucine and pyridine bases present have to be determined. This paper deals only with the pyridine bases, the estimation of which is difficult owing to their variable composition and describes the most efficient procedure for their identification and determination in denatured spirit. The three methods for determining pyridine bases are given below.

Volumetric Method.

Aqueous solutions of pyridine can be estimated volumetrically by titration with standard sulphuric acid using methyl orange, bromophenol blue or congo-red paper (as an external indicator) provided ammonia and caustic alkalis are absent. Bromophenol blue cannot be used for titrating alcoholic solutions of pyridine. When the presence of ammonia or caustic alkalis is suspected (detected by the use of red litmus paper or phenolphthalein, on which pyridine has practically no effect) the solution is exactly neutralised with $N/10$ -sulphuric acid (phenolphthalein) and then titrated for pyridine against $N/10$ -sulphuric acid using any one of the above-mentioned indicators.

To eliminate alcohol and substances such as caustic alkalis or non-volatile alkaloidal bases, which interfere in the titration with sulphuric acid, the following distillation method has been worked out.

Distillation Method.—Measure 100 ml. of the sample of denatured spirit under test into a Thorpe's revenue still and just acidify (congo-red paper)

with dilute sulphuric acid and distil until about 3 ml. of residue remain. Cool the distillation flask, add 100 ml. of distilled water and make the solution alkaline (litmus) with dilute sodium hydroxide solution, adding a few drops in excess. If pyridine is present, even in traces, its characteristic odour will be perceptible. Connect the flask again to the distillation apparatus and collect about 100 ml. of the distillate in a graduated flask making the volume up to 100 ml. with distilled water. The distillate should be neutral to phenolphthalein (ammonia absent). Titrate 10 ml. of the distillate with $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ using bromophenol blue or methyl orange as internal, or congo-red paper as an external indicator. The volume of $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ required should not be less than 4.7 ml. This limit is based on a number of determinations on spirit denatured with pyridine bases which conformed to the Government of India specifications.

Precipitation Method.

Pyridine bases in aqueous solution resemble alkaloids in giving distinct precipitates with mercuric chloride, cadmium chloride, iodine in potassium iodide solution (Harvey and Sparks, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1918, 87, 411), phosphotungstic acid, silicotungstic acid, Dragendorff's reagent (Pavolini, *Chim. Ind. Agr. Boli.*, 1931, 6, 272) and Nessler's reagent.

Preliminary tests showed that, of these reagents, cadmium chloride is the only one suitable for estimating pyridine bases in 0.5% alcoholic solution. The others either do not give any precipitate in the presence of much alcohol, or, if a precipitate forms, it only appears after long standing.

Ionescu and Slusanchi (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1933, 53, 1087) claim that the sensitiveness of the cadmium chloride reaction is proportional to the amount of reagent added, more particularly if sodium chloride is also present. They describe a method for the estimation of pyridine by measuring the time taken for a noticeable precipitate to appear when $N\text{-CdCl}_2$ in $N\text{-NaCl}$ is added to an aqueous solution of pyridine bases. The authors found that this reagent gave a well defined crystalline precipitate with alcoholic solutions of pyridine, though the reaction was somewhat delayed owing to the presence of alcohol. Hence, it cannot be applied for the estimation of pyridine bases in denatured spirit.

It was found, however, that by taking a larger quantity of the 6% aqueous solution of cadmium chloride than that prescribed in the official test (0.5 c.c.), the characteristic precipitate is obtained immediately.

The following qualitative test for the detection of pyridine bases is therefore proposed for rapid work.

Procedure.—Of the sample of denatured spirit, 15 ml. are shaken vigorously in a 25 ml. stoppered measuring cylinder with 3 ml. of a 6% solution of cadmium chloride ($\text{CdCl}_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). A characteristic white crystalline precipitate forms immediately which has no tendency to settle down on standing. It is advisable to cool the solution to about 20° though it has been observed that the test is valid up to about 37° .

Colorimetric Method.

Cyanogen bromide and aniline (Lehner, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1922, **46**, 877; Goris and Larssonau, *Bull. sci. pharmacol.*, 1922, **28**, 497), copper sulphate and ammonium thiocyanate (Spacu, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1925, **67**, 31), 2:4-dinitrochlorobenzene (Von Gerichten, *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 2571), benzenesulphonyl chloride and 2:3-diaminophenazine hydrochloride (Pavolini, *Industria Chimica*, 1932, **8**, 692) give characteristic colours in dilute solutions containing pyridine.

Cyanogen bromide forms a yellow coloured compound with pyridine and the reaction is sensitive to one part of pyridine in about 350,000 parts of water (Tallantyre, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1930, **49**, 466r). After removing alcohol and caoutchoucine, this method can be employed to determine pyridine bases in denatured spirit using the following procedure, all details of which should be meticulously observed.

Cyanogen Bromide Test.

(i) *Cyanogen Bromide Solution.*—Take 1 ml. of bromine in 100 ml. of distilled water, cool in ice and add from a burette, drop by drop, 5% solution of potassium cyanide until the colour of bromine just disappears (about 25-26 ml.). The solution prepared under these conditions has no colour (due to excess of bromine) and is not alkaline to litmus. Excess of alkali vitiates the test and should be carefully neutralised with $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. This reagent keeps well for six days but after that it decreases in its sensitiveness and should not be used.

(ii) *Saturated Solution of Aniline.*—Shake 5 ml. of freshly distilled aniline in 100 ml. of distilled water for 15 minutes and filter the supernatant liquor.

(iii) *Standard Solution of Pyridine Bases.*—Dissolve 0.5 ml. of pyridine bases satisfying the specifications laid down by the Government of India

in 40 ml. of distilled water. Neutralise exactly with $N/2\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (congo-red paper) and make up the volume to 100 ml. This control solution should be freshly prepared.

Method.—Take 10 ml. of denatured spirit under test in a basin, make it just acid (congo-red paper) with $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and evaporate on a water-bath until about 2-3 ml. remain. Add 5 ml. of distilled water to the residue and evaporate almost to dryness. Add about 20 ml. of distilled water and filter washing the basin and the filter thrice with 5 ml. of distilled water. Exactly neutralise (congo-red paper) with $N/10\text{-NaOH}$ and make up to 50 ml. Take 5 ml. of this solution in a Nessler's tube (50 ml. capacity), add 1 ml. of aniline solution and make up to 50 ml.

Simultaneously prepare a series of standard comparison tubes, each containing different volumes of the standard pyridine solution (solution iii), ranging from 0.1 to 0.01% pyridine. Cool all the test solutions to 20° , and introduce 2 ml. of cyanogen bromide solution from a burette into each of the tubes. Allow to stand for 10 minutes, stirring the solution occasionally with a glass rod and compare the yellow colour produced.

If the requisite quantity of pyridine has been added to the spirit, the colour produced in the tube containing the test solution should match that given by 5 ml. of 0.1% standard solution. The yellow colour gradually changes to orange on keeping for longer periods.